

A molecular window into the mass loss history of Luminous Blue Variables

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When massive stars ($M > 8 M_{\odot}$) leave the Main Sequence, they undergo a series of transitional stages before meeting their fate as core-collapse supernovae. In this interlude, massive stars lose a significant fraction of their initial mass, heavily altering their surroundings from a chemical and dynamical perspective. A proper characterization of this transition is thus crucial to better constrain stellar evolution and measure the impact of these evolved sources at a Galactic scale. Among these post-Main Sequence stages, the Luminous Blue Variable phase (hereafter LBV) is perhaps the most challenging one: a brief ($t \sim 10^4$ yr) episode in which the stars become unstable and exhibit the highest mass loss rates, produced by the combination of dense and steady winds, and sporadic outbursts or *eruptions*, able to expel up to a 10–20% of the stellar mass in very short timescales. These processes leave an unmistakable footprint in the surrounding ISM, triggering the formation of massive nebulae of dust and gas with strong hints of CNO processing. The study of such structures is a powerful diagnostic tool that sheds light on the elusive nature of LBV stars, allowing for an accurate reconstruction of their mass-loss record and disentangling their complex, time-dependent interaction with the ISM. For years, this work has mostly involved a synergistic approach that combines far-infrared and radio continuum observations, tracing the dust and ionised gas content of the nebulae [1, 2, 3]. While these studies have played an invaluable role to better understand the mass-loss processes of LBV stars, the global picture is still unclear, and many questions remain unanswered: the mechanisms behind the eruptions, the factors determining the shaping of the ejecta, and the total mass-loss budget are still uncertain.

The missing piece of the puzzle

The possible existence of a molecular component associated with LBV nebulae was long overlooked due to the unsuitable conditions found in the outskirts of these stars (e.g., very high temperatures, intense UV radiation beyond the Lyman limit). However, in the last two decades, a few molecular spectroscopy works challenged the accepted vision of LBV mass-loss as a two-piece puzzle. The detection of H_2 in the Homunculus Nebula around η Car [4] constituted a remarkable milestone, followed by the discovery of conspicuous circumstellar shells and hot clumps of CO [9] and NH_3 [10] around G79.29+0.46. These findings, along with a handful of loosely related structures in other sources, hinted at a non-negligible, unseen mass component that must be considered to properly characterize the interplay between LBVs –and, more generally, evolved massive stars– and the ISM. Even so, disentangling a putative circumstellar molecular gas component from nearby molecular clouds, e.g.,

telling apart compressed ISM material and molecular gas formed *in situ* out of ejecta, is only possible by the combination of indirect morpho-kinematic, physical and chemical criteria. In this respect, the detection of less abundant molecules towards the waist of the Homunculus, including N- and O-bearing species with extremely low $[^{12}C/^{13}C]$ isotopic ratios [6], set a valuable precedent, underlining the potential of LBVs as molecular polluters and paving the ground for further in-depth studies.

Spurred on by the possibility of this molecular component being a widespread feature among the LBV population, we initiated an observational campaign to search for molecular gas towards a sample of Galactic LBV stars that exhibit signposts of eruptive mass loss (i.e., circumstellar dusty nebulae).

Figure 1: Shells and rings of CO around LBV stars.

A story of shells and rings

The main outcome of this campaign is the detection of a new type of structure associated with LBV stars: large, slowly expanding CO rings, found around the sources MN101 [11] and AG Car [12] –observed with the IRAM-30m telescope, and with APEX and ALMA, respectively. The rings, depicted in Figure 1, bottom panels, have sizes of 0.2 and 0.4 pc, and show strikingly low expansion velocities, of less than 5 km s^{-1} . This value, barely supersonic, is extremely puzzling, falling below the typical expansion velocities of LBV nebulae (~ 1 dex). Employing non-LTE radiative transfer modelling, we estimated the physical conditions of the rings. The molecular gas is relatively diffuse ($n_{H_2} \sim 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$), warm ($T_k \sim 50 \text{ K}$) and moderately optically-thick ($\tau \sim 1$), showing notable differences with respect to nearby interstellar clouds. The rings seem to be aligned with the equatorial plane of the stars –which has been confirmed for AG Car–, thereby tracing some sort of equatorial density enhancement. However, pinpointing the exact origin of the molecules is tricky. As discussed above, they could have arisen from interstellar material piled up by the stellar wind, or from stellar ejecta. The $[^{12}C/^{13}C]$ ratios measured in the two rings –using $[^{12}CO/^{13}CO]$ as a proxy–, lower than

the standard ISM value and hence suggesting a moderate degree of CNO processing, may support the ejection scenario. Moreover, the masses of the rings are also consistent with a stellar origin, being 0.6 ± 0.1 and $2.7 \pm 0.9 M_{\odot}$ for MN101 and AG Car, respectively. As thoroughly discussed in [13], binarity and fast rotation seem to favour the formation of these rings. While MN101 is an almost unexplored object, AG Car is a well characterized LBV, known to be a fast rotator. Changes in the wind properties at low latitudes due to the nearly critical rotation and subsequent gravity darkening may induce a slower and denser wind near the equator, in which molecules could form and survive more efficiently. Similarly, the presence of a companion, as recently proposed following VLT observations [15], could result in non-conservative mass transfer episodes that would lead to the formation of an expanding ring. Nevertheless, these hypotheses need further observations and modelling work to be confirmed.

In contrast to these equatorial rings, we also found molecular structures that follow a remarkably isotropic distribution. Using APEX, we identified several shells of CO around MN48, a LBV that constitutes the best analogue of G79.29+0.46: the central star is surrounded by a shallow dusty shell, allegedly interacting with a nearby HII region (Figure 1, top panels). As in G79.29+0.46, the molecular shells, with a mass of $\sim 10 M_{\odot}$, show dynamical signatures of interaction towards the SW [14].

The uniqueness of η Car

η Car is a special object, a massive binary system composed of a $\sim 100 M_{\odot}$ LBV, and a less massive ($\sim 30 M_{\odot}$) companion. The LBV underwent a violent outburst in the mid 19th century, nicknamed the Great Eruption, perhaps triggered by a merger in a triple system. This cataclysmic event gave birth to the Homunculus Nebula, a massive bipolar nebula expanding at very high speeds. Sitting in the waist of the Homunculus, there is a partially disrupted circumstellar torus ($r \sim 4000$ au), resolved in CO [5, 12] (Figure 1, right panel). This torus, dynamically linked to the Great Eruption ($v_{\text{exp}} \sim 120 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) is the main molecular reservoir of η Car [7]. Analysing ALMA band 7 archival observations, we disclosed the HCN and HCO⁺ counterpart of the CO torus, along with molecular emission in the region of the so-called inner ejecta, debris expelled in a lesser eruption in the 1890s. As shown in [12], this emission arises from "hot bullets" of HCN -detected also in their vibrationally-excited transitions-, located extremely close to the central stars, a hostile region where other molecules have been reported [8].

Implications and prospects

Our results consolidate the evidence that survival of molecules in the outskirts of LBV stars is the norm rather than the exception. Molecular gas is a key ingredient of

the CSM around LBV stars, and more importantly, it conveys an essential side of their mass-loss history. From shells to rings, the study of this component opens a path to disclose the complex interplay between evolved massive stars and their surroundings. In those cases where molecular gas can be confidently linked to stellar ejecta, we proved that it may represent a substantial fraction of the total mass loss budget ($\geq 30\%$), thus having important repercussions on stellar evolution models, very sensitive to the adopted mass-loss rates. Finally, regarding the intriguing rings of MN101 and AG Car, and their much younger "relative" in η Car, we combined our results with literature data of other (dusty) rings around LBV-like objects, finding an empirical relation that suggests a common dynamical scenario, in which the same type of structure evolves in similar environments (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Radius versus expansion velocity of LBV rings.

Taken altogether, these results highlight the important role of mm/sub-mm spectroscopy in building an accurate portrait of the CSM around evolved massive stars. This has profound astrophysical implications, reframing the role of evolved massive stars as molecular factories, and improving the current understanding of the environment where core-collapse supernovae take place.

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